

Defining Intent-based Service Management Automation for 6G Multi-stakeholders Scenarios

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ABSTRACT This article aims to explore the requirements and challenges that Intent-Based Management (IBM) systems should look towards to deliver proper automation management in multi-stakeholder 6G scenarios. To do so, the evolution of the telecommunications actors is presented to identify how they will interact with the use of intents and what IBM systems must face to fulfil with the tenants expectations while interacting among other IBM domains (aggregation vs. federation models). In a second step, this article presents how the IBM systems functionalities should be organized (based on standards research and comparative) and a set of enablers using them to properly deliver the automation needed to accomplish the requests done by the tenants. On a third step, a set of End-to-End (E2E) intent-based services are described to illustrate how the different enablers (and the functionalities they use) may work to reach the E2E service goal. Finally, a set of experimental results related to how intent conflicts should be manage is presented, followed by the conclusions.

INDEX TERMS intent-based networks, 6G, multi-stakeholder, end-to-end services

I. INTRODUCTION

The expectation for 6G is to support a wide range of future scenarios, encompassing various services such as online gaming, AR/VR, intelligent transportation systems, and smart cities [1]. These challenging services necessitate optimizing network providers' operational efficiency to reduce costs while meeting new requirements. Achieving this high level of efficiency requires extensive adoption of

network automation, which minimizes the need for human intervention. In this context, zero-touch operations fully exploit automation to create management processes that continuously optimize resource allocation, ensuring the entire network remains in an optimal state while addressing dynamic functional and non-functional requirements.

A key difference in delivering new 6G services lies in the increasingly dynamic nature of operating requirements.

Consequently, the methods for translating these requirements into network decisions and actions must evolve. It is crucial for service providers to adopt new forms of representing and communicating the expectations from the users to facilitate this translation. Rather than relying on policies and other imperative forms of communication, high-level abstractions should be used to enable the translation of requirements across management layers and multiple domains that comprise the end-to-end (E2E) service.

With this aim, Intent-based networking (IBN) emerges as a pivotal instrument for the management of such complexity of networks and services within the forthcoming generation of networks [2] [3]. Intents have primarily been utilized in IT and networking within the context of software-defined networks (SDN). The main goal was to develop a high-level abstraction layer that simplifies the expression of commands and configurations, enabling the selection of policies within SDN controllers [4].

The intent is also considered for autonomous networking and Internet Research Task Force (IRTF) defined intent as “an abstract, high-level policy to operate a network” in 2015 [5]. However, later this definition has evolved, and the intent is defined as “a set of operational goals that a network should meet and outcomes that a network is supposed to deliver, defined in a declarative manner without specifying how to achieve or implement them” [6]. As agreed on the final definition, intents carry the high-level expectation of a service (i.e., throughput or latency), and are declarative stating the desired state but not how to achieve it.

To this end, the main point on implementing the use of intents is to assist and simplify how services are requested, decreasing the level of technical knowledge that the requesters need to have to ask for the deployment of a specific service. This becomes even more crucial in the next generation of networks with the appearance of the multi-stakeholder scenario. Within this scenario, due to the diversity of the requirements and capabilities offered by the different actors, tenants face a more complex scenario to determine what do they exactly need and how do they should request it. An IBN solution should be used to assist the tenants with their requests. Leaving to the IBN system the role to identify what is needed and by which actor can be done in an autonomous way.

The use of IBN aims not only to facilitate the way the tenant and the system understand each other by abstracting technical parameters for the tenant, but also to promote the use of autonomous systems that avoid the need to have human intervention to decide how and which resources should be used. To this end, IBN systems are expected to be capable to interact with lower layers (i.e., domain resource managers) and based on the information these elements deliver, to decide which domain is the most suitable to deliver (i.e., resources available) and ensure (i.e., monitor) the requested service and the expected quality associated.

This paper aims to extend the work presented in [7] by moving the focus from the management of intent-based services in a single administrative domain to how intents should be managed and orchestrated in multi-stakeholder scenarios with different domains involved. Moreover, to properly extend and identify the requirements and challenges that these foreseen scenarios will expect, a set of E2E intent-based services use cases are presented. To this end, the contributions this paper brings are:

- A design and definition of how different kinds of tenants may interact with the IBN provider systems to define intents and obtain the desired service based on the requirements and needs of the multiple stakeholders involved in the process.
- The evolution, compared to [7], of the key functionalities that an IBN management component must have and offer to the tenants in order to properly deliver a complete IBN solution.
- A set of identified E2E services where IBN should bring most of its advantages and simplify the management of resources of the multiple stakeholders and generate trust among them.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a description of how telecommunication actors are expected to evolve to enable the expected 6G multi-stakeholder scenarios, including the definition of their roles and how they should participate in the management of intent-based services. Section III illustrates how the actor in charge of the intent-based services management (i.e., Digital Service Provider (DSP)) may act depending on the type of tenants (i.e., users) requesting intents and on the relationship with other DSPs from other administrative domains. The focus of this section is to present the two models to orchestrate intent-based services across different domains and their strengths and weaknesses. Section IV presents the Intent-based Digital Service Manager component used by the DSP and its main functions. Moreover, a proposed set of enablers (i.e., a designed solution that focuses a subset of the functions, e.g., a reporting enabler) based on the identified functions to offer the complete life cycle of an intent is described. Moreover, introduces the set of security enablers that should ensure the protection of the resources used to deliver the intent-based services. To properly show how the presented actors, components, functions and enablers interplay, Section V illustrates a set of use case examples in which different combinations of the previously introduced enablers are used to accomplish multiple E2E intent-based management services. Then, Section VI presents an experimental evaluation of how intent-based conflicts may affect and should be managed in multi-stakeholder scenarios. Finally, Section VII summarizes the most important ideas and draws some conclusions.

II. AN INTENT-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR TECHCOS

To study and evaluate the requirements and needs of intent-based systems, it is key to understand the current situation of

the telecommunications (telco) environment and how Telco Organizations are expected to evolve their systems towards 6G systems, especially regarding their management and orchestration. With this scope in mind, this section aims to describe how intent-based systems may affect their relationships with both the tenants (users) on top and their peers on the side. To do so, this section presents the evolution of Telco Organizations towards Technology Companies (TechCos) [8] and the necessary use of intents by these entities, in interactions ranging from the tenants to the specific domain resource managers.

A. TOWARDS a TECHCOS ECOSYSTEM

Telco systems are complex, involving the administration, operation and maintenance (OAM) of a myriad of hardware and software resources that are i) deployed and installed in a distributed infrastructure; ii) combined into cloud and network functions, which collectively support the execution of end-to-end (E2E) communication services to multiple customers, from different market segments. The creation of simplicity out of this complex ecosystem requires applying the principles of abstraction and separation of concerns when designing these systems. Taking these recommendations into account, Tier-1 telcos (i.e., large mobile network operators worldwide) typically structure their OAM systems into different layers, each with a confined scope that can evolve independently from the rest of the layers.

In the definition of actor-role model for 5G [9] [10], 3GPP notes two main roles in telco ecosystem:

- Network Operator (NOP), focused on managing network and cloud resources, and their composition into upper-layer network constructions, including domain-specific (e.g., sub-networks, network slice subnets) and E2E constructions (e.g., network slices).
- Communication Service Provider (CSP), focusing on building communication services and delivering them to targeted customers, including end-users (i.e., Business to Consumer -B2C-), enterprise customers (i.e., Business to Business -B2B-) or other CSPs (i.e., B2B to X -B2B2X-).

Tier-1 telcos typically embrace both roles, mapping them to different organization's units. In the telco system architecture, one can easily note that i) control layer is within the scope of NOP; ii) commercial layer is within the scope of CSP; iii) the network & service management layer is targeted by NOP and CSP, the former focusing on management of domain specific and E2E network constructions, and the latter on design, provisioning, and assurance of communication services.

In the 6G ecosystem, it is expected for Tier-1 telcos to become TechCos [8], with a wider scope on service offerings, and further flexibility on the composition and operation of managed resources. This means:

- TechCos service offering will not be limited to communication services (collection of PDU sessions exchanged between devices and data networks), but to other digital services (e.g., Web3, big data, security services). All these services will be also offered to new customers through APIs (instead of traditional channels). This change motivates the transition from CSP to DSP.
- TechCos will articulate their systems with much more granularity, breaking functions into their fundamental components (microservices), each representing stand-alone capabilities that can be individually programmed and chained on a per service/use case needs. This, alongside the ever-increasing offloading models in telco industry (e.g., with new emerging actors such as TowerCos, FiberCos, neutral hosts), also motivates the NOP role decomposition into capability operator (COP) and resource provider roles.

B. INTENT-BASED DIGITAL SERVICE MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the E2E intent-based service management automation framework developed in HEXA-X-II involves different actors and entities. With the objective to enable the transition to the "TechCo" ecosystem, the framework is designed with four layers: a) the Digital Service Customers (DSC) (i.e., tenants) on top, b) the DSP, which is a 5G CSP extension, c) the Capability Operator (COP) layer (e.g., Network, Cloud, AI, etc.) and, finally, d) the Resource Providers layer.

The DSP and the COP may belong to the same administrative domain (e.g. Telefónica or Orange), while the Resource providers can belong to third parties. The DSP is the main interlocutor for the different existing types of tenants, defined as follows within the proposed E2E vision:

- Tenant-1 type: An aggregator tenant that follows the B2B2X model and offers the intent-based services to a second type of tenants with a B2B model. Examples of Tenant-1 type are Hyperscaler Marketplaces, Telco Consortiums, etc.
- Tenant-2 type: This type of tenant regroups either Verticals following a B2B model such as an XR provider, or Application Service Providers following a Business to Business to Consumer (B2B2C) model. These two possible tenants obtain the intent-based services through the interaction with aggregator (tenant-type 1).
- Tenant-3 type: Verticals may be a third type of tenants having direct access to the offered intent-based services, for example banking companies.

These three types of tenants interact (directly or not) at the DSP layer with the Intent-based Digital Service Manager (DSM) component through the Intent-DSC API. This interaction results on the generation of the intent-based requests [11] [12]. These requests should be created with the

FIGURE 1. E2E Digital Service Management Automation Framework

expectations and targets that define the expected service for the final user by selecting the available COPs and Resource Providers below. At the DSP layer, the DSM is placed at each single administrative domain leading the management (i.e., provisioning, monitoring, etc.) of intents using the resources offered in the layers below by the capability operators and providers through an Integration Fabric (IF) component as defined by the ETSI Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM) group in [13].

While one single DSP offers a wide range of services, it is expected that it will not always be able to deliver all the services. For this reason, a federation approach was taken into consideration when designing the E2E DSM framework to allow the interaction of different DSP through their Intent-based DSM, using an east-west interface called “Intent-DSP API”. Regarding the internal architecture of functions and capabilities offered by the Intent-based DSM, this topic is properly addressed in the following section.

The third identified actor within the framework are the COPs, which are operating those entities/elements in charge of managing the domain resources available. A COP is handling the control and management elements such as a Network Slice Management Function (NSMF) or other domains specific managers. The communication between the DSP and the COP layers is done through the IF.

Finally, the last layer involves the Resource Providers across different domains. The Resource Providers offer a set of different domain resources such as applications, AI, network (including RAN, transport, and core) and finally, cloud resources (extreme-edge, edge, and cloud). The type of available resources that each single administrative domain

manages may vary depending on the needs - Fig. 1 illustrates one of the many possibilities.

III. TOWARDS A DSM FOR MULTI-STAKEHOLDER SCENARIO

Because of the different types of tenants identified in the multi-stakeholder scenario, two models for the intent-based service provisioning were identified: a) the aggregation model, which leaves to one of the tenants all the responsibility to request the multiple required intents, as it has the direct contact with the Intent-based DSM of all the available administrative domains, and b) the federation model, which moves this responsibility to the Intent-based DSM of the single administrative domain that has received the request from the tenant. In this case, the Intent-based DSM is in charge of interacting with Intent-based DSMs from other single administrative domains and to request the necessary intents.

In order to fully understand the workflows associated to these two models (Fig. 2, Fig. 3), it is important to be aware that in both figures the interactions that the Intent-based DSM has with the rest of its single administrative domain components (i.e., Service Orchestrators, Resource Manages, etc.) is resumed with a red note to make the figures clearer and focus on the differences between the two presented models.

For better understanding of the differences of the two models, the description of both workflows is based on the same use case where a vertical service (e.g., video-streaming, gaming session, etc.) is needed to be offered to a set of users in domain B. So, in both figures, the roles of the Digital Service Customers (DSC) (i.e., where tenants are)

FIGURE 2. Multi-DSP AGGREGATION intent-based service provisioning workflow.

and the Single Administrative Domains (SAD) (i.e., where the Intent-based DSMs are) that offer their resources to the DSCs can be distinguished.

A. MULTI-DSP AGGREGATION SERVICE PROVISIONING

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the aggregation model begins (step 1) when a Tenant-2 Type (e.g., Vertical Business) requests to a Tenant-1 Type (i.e., Aggregator) the service that it intends to deliver towards its clients (i.e., vertical clients/final users).

From that moment, the Tenant-1 Type is in charge to properly ask the right intents to the best available SAD possible. In the example used to describe this workflow, the request specifies “users in domain B”, so the Tenant-1 Type could simply ask to domain B if it has the required resources (i.e., vertical service connectivity service, etc.), but as the Tenant-1 Type does not know what is available,

first it must ask to all domains. To do so, it requests all known SADs by requesting intents to get the available capabilities offered by each of them (steps 2 – 4). Based on the received information from each SAD, the Tenant-1 Type will identify and select the best domain capability for each expectation within the received “step 1” intent from the Tenant-2 Type (step 5). To do so, the selection should be based on: a) the availability of the services in each SAD (i.e., if they have the service to deliver the vertical one), b) the capacity to achieve the Key Performance Indicators and key Value Indicators (KPIs/KVIs), and finally, c) other possible resources information (e.g., related to load distribution) that the SADs may share.

Once the Tenant-1 Type knows which specific intents to request to each SAD, (e.g., vertical service to SAD A and a connectivity service from the SAD A to SAD B), the Tenant-

1 Type begins to request them to the corresponding intent-based Digital Service Manager (DSM) of each SAD (steps 6 and 13). While all intents are managed independently by each assigned intent-based DSM, their correct performance may depend on one another; for this reason, the Tenant-1 Type must know in which order it needs to request each intent. In the example illustrated in Fig. 2, first the vertical service is requested to the SAD A (step 6). The intent-based DSM in the SAD A will receive it and process it (step 7) to: a) identify the expectations composing the intent and validate them with the KPIs/KVIs based on the Service level Agreements (SLAs) contracted between the SAD A and the Tenant-1 Type, and b) to create and store the intent data object.

When the intent request is processed and its expectations validated, the Tenant-1 Type is notified about this (step 8) and the intent-based DSM follows with the intent provisioning. To accomplish the full intent provisioning the intent-based DSM will need to map the multiple expectations composing the incoming intent into a set of executable services (step 9). Then, the intent-based DSM must evaluate the feasibility of the identified expectations checking the local resources (Step 10) and if the answer is affirmative, the intent is deployed locally (red note) as presented in [7]. Afterwards, once each expectation is fulfilled and no conflicts detected (or solved), the intent data object is updated (step 11) and the Tenant-1 Type (i.e., intent owner) is notified with an intent report (step 12).

At this point, the first intent is completed, and the Tenant-1 Type may proceed with the following intent requests based on the selection of SADs done in step 5. The procedure for this second intent, now in SAD B, follows the same steps as the procedure just described: starting from step 13 with the reception of the intent request by the intent-based DSM in the SAD B, until step 19 with the report notification of the expectation fulfilment status and possible conflicts.

Finally, once all identified intents are properly deployed and configured, the Tenant-1-Type is able to inform the Tenant-2 Type that its requests have been properly achieved and the vertical service is ready to be used by its final users.

B. MULTI-DSP FEDERATION SERVICE PROVISIONING

The federation model aims to remove the need for an aggregator role, leaving the responsibility to identify and select which SADs should participate to the intent-based DSM in the SAD receiving the initial intent-based request from the tenant actor.

This main difference can be seen in the workflow presented in Fig. 3. On the one hand, now, the tenants request directly to the intent-based DSM the complete intent request to obtain the vertical service that will be offered to the final (i.e., vertical) users, avoiding the need of an aggregator. On the other hand, the intent-based DSM receiving the initial request is the one in charge to interact with other intent-based DSMs to get their assistance, if necessary, to deploy

the expected resources to accomplish the intent requested by the tenant.

With these two main aspects in mind, the federated service provisioning model begins with the Tenant-3 Type requesting the intent-based requests with the (E2E) vertical service requirements (step 1) to the intent-based DSM who is the point of contact for the requesting tenant. Then, this component will begin with the same actions as in the other model such as processing the incoming requests to identify and validate the expectations, and to create and store the intent (step 2).

While a notification is sent back to the tenant about the acceptance of the request (step 3), the intent-based DSM follows with the provisioning procedure by mapping the intent to executable services (step 4) and the feasibility evaluation of the identified expectations with the DSM local resources (step 5). At this point the main difference compared to the aggregation model appears: the “east-west” interaction with the intent-based DSMs from other domains.

If an expectation is feasible using local resources, the same intent-based DSM manages its deployment (red note) following the procedure already described in [7]. On the contrary, if resources (i.e., services or capabilities) are not available locally, the intent-based DSM requests the available capabilities and services from other known SADs (steps 6 and 7) and based on the responses, it selects the most appropriate domains to request those expectations that could not be implemented locally (step 8). To do so, the selection is based on the service and resources availability together with the KPIs/KVIs needed and offered.

Then, once the domain for each “non-local” expectation is identified, an intent-based provisioning procedure (steps 9 – 14) is triggered between intent-based DSMs that follows the same steps already presented in the previous Fig. 2 (e.g., steps 6 to 12, 13 to 19).

Finally, once all the non-local expectations are properly fulfilled through the provisioning of “federated” intents, the original intent-based DSM is able to update its “E2E” intent data object (Step 15) and notify the Tenant-3 Type, which in its own time and following internal procedures, will deliver the access information of the deployed vertical service to its final users.

C. MODELS STRENGTHS & WEAKNESSES

In both cases the complexity is high as the illustrated processes from the two models involve the participation of multiple administrative domains to address digital service requests, considering both local and cross-domain capabilities, together with a set of individually complex tasks such as intent identification, validation, mapping to executable services, feasibility evaluation, and conflict resolution.

Overall, these workflows outline two different ways to manage intents that require the participation of different domains without the need to let the verticals (i.e., Tenant-2 or Tenant-3 Types) know how to fully accomplish the

FIGURE 3. Multi-DSP FEDERATION intent-based service provisioning workflow.

requested intent. While in the first model (i.e., aggregation) the management of the whole process is done hierarchically by the Tenant-1 Type (i.e., aggregator), in the second model (i.e., federation) the management is done from a more collaborative point of view among the multiple intent-based DSMs placed across the different SADs, removing the responsibility to orchestrate from the tenant and moving it to the intent-based DSMs to interact with other intent-based DSMs from the rest of the SADs.

In terms of automation, the federation model goes one step further compared to the aggregation model as it leaves to the intent-based DSM in charge to interact among them to

find the best suitable domain combination to fulfill the intent requested by the tenant. While it is a strength in terms of automation, this aspect adds another complexity layer to the intent-based management and orchestration.

IV. INTENT-BASED DIGITAL SERVICE MANAGEMENT DESIGN

While in the previous section, the focus was on the multi-stakeholder scenario and how the different actors interact and manage the multi-domain relationships to achieve a complete and stable intent-based service provisioning, this section aims to present and introduce the internal aspects

that an intent-based DSM must have to properly manage the provisioning of intents within the scope of its SAD. To this end, this section presents the DSM functional architecture. Then, it presents a set of enablers, each specifically designed to accomplish a set of the functionalities within the architecture here presented. Finally, an analysis on how the designed architecture considers the interfaces defined by different standard organizations is presented.

A. FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE

Based on the guidelines from the 3GPP [14] [3] [13] and as illustrated in Fig. 4, a functional architecture is proposed for the intent-based DSM component previously illustrated in the multi-stakeholder scenario. This innovative functional architecture, called DSM-Intent Management Entity (IME) is structured in 7 functional blocks and interacts with the Service Management Domains (MDs) and the Resources MDs through an IF.

The presented functional architecture has evolved since its first version in [7]. In this subsection, we focus on the architecture itself and identify the novelties compared to the one in [7]. Later in subsection IV.D, the justification for these evolutions is described. Internally, the DSM-IME has the following modules:

- 1) Intent Interface: It is the gateway for the user to interact with the whole intent management solution and the architecture core element as it takes care of the intents data objects with the multiple actions to control the intent's life cycle. It offers the following capabilities: the "Intent Interpreter" to process the incoming requests from the user and let DSM-IME understand what is intended; the "Intent Handling Capability Exposure" which allows the system to present to the user what the system is capable to offer and manage through the use of intents; the "Intent CRUD" (Create/Read/Update/Delete) to offer the set of operations to trigger the different processes to manage intents; the "Intent Report Management" to offer the methods related to the expected reporting of intents in relation with the Intent Reporting functional block; and finally, one of the evolutions compared to the previous design in [7], the "Intent ADSR" (Activate/Deactivate/Suspend/ Resume) to manage those actions that allow to keep intents alive but as alive in standby until they are required again. This functionality has been integrated following a complete analysis of the current standards and requirements presented later in subsection IV.C.
- 2) Intent Fulfilment Internals: This functional block is composed of capabilities that a user should never be able to access but that are key to those capabilities visible to the user. Among the capabilities in this module the "Intent Translation" maps the intent and its expected key performance indicators (KPIs) and key value indicators (KVI) into a set of executable service management tasks and policies from a contracted Service Level Agreement SLA, the "Intent Feasibility Check" ensures that a received intent request may be properly executed. The "Intent Closed Loop (CL) Governance and Coordination Service" has two main objectives: a) it triggers the necessary set of "Intent-driven CL Control for fulfilment evaluation" instances associated to each requested intent in order to ensure the correct deployment and to fulfill the expected requirements, and b) it offers the capability to control in a coordinated way the co-existence of multiple CLs [15] within the DSM-IME. Finally, the "Intent Conflict Detection/Resolution" identifies if a new intent or an action over an existing intent may affect negatively other existing intents. In case of a conflict between two or more intents, this service resolves it.
- 3) Intent Reporting: These functional block capabilities handle the multiple types of intent-related information. The "Intent Feasibility Check Information" presents whether it is feasible to deploy an intent or not (e.g., with the current resources available), the "Intent Fulfilment Information" gathers the intent fulfilment status and the associated target achieved values. Finally, the "Intent Conflict Information" handles information with the conflicts and their resolution.
- 4) Intent Negotiation: This functional block represents the second main evolution from the work done in [7]. It allows the DSM-IME users to obtain the precise information about the intents they might need before they are even provisioned. To this end, the internal functionalities involve: a) to probe an intent to explore if it is possible to fulfill all its expectations; the tenant would know whether or not the expectations could be fulfilled, b) to let the tenant to ask for the intent with the most severe requirements that it can manage successfully (this is quite related to the feasibility functionality), and finally, c) to formulate hypothetical outcomes for alternative actions (i.e., preferences) as base for a judgment decision to evaluate alternative outcomes corresponding to other solution strategies and actions (before these actions are executed). This last function requires predictive capabilities able to estimate the effect of the action on the system state.
- 5) Intent SLA: This functional block is another important evolution compared to [7], it contains the 3rd Party (3P) Profiling and the Service Portfolio. They both deal with the management of Service Level Agreements (SLAs) for the intents. On the one hand, the 3P Profiling provides a tenant (i.e., a 3rd party) full characterization through a 3P profile. This captures tenant-specific data on security (supported credentials and access control solutions), trustworthiness (relevant in federation scenarios), and end-users profiling data based on the contracted services and SLAs. On the other hand, the Service Portfolio offers an abstracted

FIGURE 4. DSM-IME functional architecture

information of the available 6G services information and offered SLAs (i.e., product catalogue) to the tenants, so that based on that, tenants may formulate more precise and adequate intent-requests. Available service information covers aspects such as service status (i.e., defined, designed, built, tested, released, etc.), owner, variabilities over the same service (i.e., SLA offerings, etc.), costs or dependencies with other services, etc.

- 6) Intent-driven CL Control for fulfilment evaluation: This functional block offers the capabilities to manage the intent CL instances life cycle and ensure they are fulfilled at any time. Once an Intent CL instance is created, it has the following capabilities associated to it: a) the “Intent CL Governance Service” offers the orchestration capability to control any action involving its assigned intent instance, b) the “Intent CL Execution” executes any task commanded by the governance service, c) the “Intent CL Analytics (KPI & KVI)” is the capability to process monitored metrics and generate insights from it, d) the “Intent CL Decision” makes use of the insights generated to select the most suitable decision about the intent CL instance status, e) the “Intent CL Monitoring” is the capability to acquire data and metrics related to defined KPIs to be properly analyzed by the “Intent CL Analytics (KPI & KVI)” capability, and finally, f) the “Intent CL Data Services” is the capability to store the information-related to each specific intent CL instance.
- 7) Data Services: This functional block is in charge of storing the intent data objects and other possible information such as SLAs and policies.

Finally, as introduced previously, all these functional blocks interact with the Service MDs and Resource MDs to accomplish an E2E intent-based management of the service requested by the different tenants. As presented, the communications among the DSM-IME and the Service MDs and Resources MDs are done using a Cross-domain IF, which may allow the possibility to exchange information among different solutions using a harmonized protocol.

B. MULTI-STAKEHOLDERS’ INTENT CONFLICTS MANAGEMENT

In a multi-stakeholder scenario, where a DSP may receive intents with different intent expectation targets from various verticals, it is critical to assess varied intent expectations and targets set by these verticals. Addressing these intents alongside their corresponding expectation targets can lead to conflicts. For example, achieving a throughput target for a service from a particular vertical may negatively impact reliability target of another service from the same or different vertical. Hence, the management of conflicts becomes of absolute importance, as it assists on the co-existence of the different intent-based services when two of them aim to be applied to the same resource and are not compatible. To this end, it is key to detect conflicts and to handle their resolution.

Moreover, DSPs will have to face conflicts affecting intents related not only to their own domain, but with other DSPs’ domains. To this end, the “Intent Negotiation” functionalities offered through the East-West interfaces should allow to properly mitigate intent-based conflicts among the federation of DSPs. When this may happen, two possibilities could be designed: a) a dynamic model where the DSPs should establish a common policy agreed by all of them regarding how they should act, or b) a static model with

pre-defined policies agreed prior to any conflict. In any case, the agreed policy should ensure that no single DSP's performance is negatively affected in relation to its tenants compared to other DSPs, unless justified by specific reasons.

To this end, it is important to evaluate and investigate the potential parameters and the trade-offs that define conflict resolution strategies that DSPs should agree among them, or at least announce to the others. An initial experimental evaluation is done in section VI to demonstrate how the provisioning of intent-based network slices with different requirements may lead to conflicts among them. The obtained results should provide clues so DSPs can identify which policies want to follow within their domain and advertise to other DSPs how they would behave in front of conflicts.

C. ENABLERS FOR AN INTENT-BASED AND AUTOMATED SERVICE MANAGEMENT & ORCHESTRATION

Based on the different main functionalities presented, a set of enablers was designed to be part of an intent-based DSM solution. While some of the enablers focus on a specific function (e.g., intent reporting) others aimed for a more cross-functionality (e.g., intent translation and provisioning). To this end, a short description of each enabler is presented to assist the reader towards the different intent-based E2E service management & orchestration use cases presented in section V. Further details about the different enablers may be found in [16]:

- 1) Intent Translation & Provisioning involves reaching an agreement with the user to create the intent data object and translating it into machine-based requests, considering various resource domain managers. This solution manages service resources across multiple domains, selecting the most suitable combination to deploy end-to-end services while considering service, security, trust levels, and domain constraints. Due to the innovations added since [7], this enabler will now include the Intent Negotiation functionality as it reaches agreements with the tenants.
- 2) Data Fusion Mechanisms based on Telemetry Data provides intent achievement values and supports intent-driven orchestration. This enabler collects heterogeneous observability signals based on OpenTelemetry standards for early anomaly identification and causality analysis. It supports failure identification and mitigation in applications, networks, and infrastructure, assisting with real-time intent-based mechanisms and calculating intent fulfillment values.
- 3) Closed-Loop Coordination ensures zero-touch coordination of multiple CLs for automatic intent management at the DSP level. It integrates solutions for automatic coordination of multiple CLs during the lifecycle management of intents. Conflict resolution is managed by Intent Conflict Administration (ICA), which provides instructions to enforce policies and

configurations for conflict resolution or mitigation. The CL coordination activity can be extended under certain circumstances, to other entities the DSP relies on, such as the Capability Operator (see section V.C).

- 4) Intent Conflict Administration detects conflicts between intents, informs tenants about these conflicts, and provides solutions to manage them. It addresses the negative impacts of different KPIs from various intents, proposing automatic solutions for conflict management and informing tenants when conflicts are detected.
- 5) Human-machine Intent Interface Design fulfills the need for intent-based interfaces that express application needs and requirements to networks and provide system feedback to applications. It focuses on dynamic interactions where application needs are efficiently expressed, networks adapt to human and application inputs, and timely, meaningful feedback is provided.
- 6) Intent-driven Placement proposes extensions to intent descriptions and associated analysis and decision mechanisms to guide high-level compute placement across the compute continuum. It includes intent-based extensions to microservice descriptors for specifying infrastructure component features or execution domains, and mechanisms to derive and request orchestration from execution domains, maintaining a closed loop to adjust placement according to the intent.
- 7) Declarative Intent Reconciliation ensures intent specifications and delivery workflows are consistent, up-to-date, and effectively translated into actionable configurations across multiple management domains. This enabler employs a declarative approach to describe, modify, and version-control intent specifications, and define pipelines to streamline the intent lifecycle management across intra-DSP or cross-DSP components operated by different stakeholders.
- 8) Intent Reporting provides tenants with the ability to consume intent reports from DSPs. It specifies the details an intent report should contain and how these details can be captured into an information model. This enabler allows tenants to verify and audit intent fulfillment across the entire lifecycle, with DSPs reporting progress according to the tenant-specified conditions.
- 9) 3rd Party Facing Services delivers solutions for characterizing tenants and service offerings under the DSP realm, facilitating service delivery. For each tenant accessing the system, the DSP creates and manages a third-party profile, linking service offerings to tenants according to well-defined SLAs.

D. DSP ARCHITECTURE EVOLUTION: STANDARD INTERFACES

To support E2E services with multiple DSPs (i.e., a federation of DSPs), it is necessary to evolve the proposed DSP architecture, as shown in Fig. 1. Hence, it is required

to evaluate the current framework to know if it is possible to support the federation of DSPs. This evaluation includes analyzing the current intent interface, as shown in Fig. 4. To do this, a divide-and-conquer approach is considered to evaluate each block of the intent interface in Fig. 4. For each interface block (e.g., Intent Interpreter, Intent CRUD, etc.) we describe the functionality covered by it; then, we map it to enablers previously identified in [7], finally we map it to standard interfaces to check if it matches the functionality of one of the existing APIs. Next, we describe the blocks.

The Intent interpreter block creates an intent object from a request. It is related to the Intent Translation & Provisioning and the Human-machine Intent Interface enablers design and related to the SET interface of several standards such as TM Forum and 3GPP [2] [3].

The Intent Handling Capability Exposure block assists a user by showing services offered towards the user. It is related also to intent translation and provisioning and to the TM Forum standard Intent Manager Capability Profile [2] [17].

The Intent CRUD contains the set of actions such as Create, Read, etc. It is related to the CRUD in CLs, and the intent report management, and the translation and provisioning for enablers. For the standards, multiple APIs as SET, REMOVE, REPORT are presented among others [2] [3].

The next block of Intent Activation/Deactivation allows intent to make it run and to keep it in standby until it is required. It is related to the Intent Translation & Provisioning enabler, the Intent Activation/Deactivation, and to ZSM activation/deactivation/suspension API [9].

Finally, the Intent Report Management offers the actions related to the expected reporting of intents. It is related to the Intent reporting enabler and to the standardized interface for Intent report. We can summarize the results of the evaluation in Table 1.

The evaluation of the previous DSM design revealed that the Intent Interface in [7] is missing functionalities that should allow negotiation between tenants and DSPs (i.e., DSMs) on the North-Bound Interface (NBI). Additionally, it lacks the negotiation capabilities required between DSPs for a federation of DSPs (i.e., East-West interfaces). For this reason, the Intent Interface properly evolved with the addition of the “Intent ADSR” functionality”. Comparing the three standard interfaces (Table 1), two functionalities from the “setting the intent” block were missing (i.e., Suspend/Resume) together with the complete “negotiating an intent” block. To solve this issue, as previously introduced, the “Intent ADSR” functional block was added together with the “Intent Negotiation” module, bringing to the designed DSM the capacity to interact in an east-west federated way with other DSM from other DSPs, as shown in Fig. 4.

E. SECURING THE MANAGEMENT OF INTENT-BASED SERVICES

In the context of multi-DSP federation service provisioning, multitude security issues can occur due to the federation of resources across different administrative domains at the same time. Moreover, it may cause the transferring of security vulnerabilities from one domain to another if proper isolation is not achieved. This potential transmission of vulnerabilities can complicate the identification of the source of the threat and the detection of the administrative domain responsible for a particular security issue. However, the complex nature of resource federation may create challenges in applying isolation techniques in practice and tracking the root cause and the origin of security breaches. To provide robust and secure service federation as mentioned above, it is necessary to incorporate continuous monitoring and security assessment to ensure E2E security. This includes developing dynamic and adaptive security solutions for threat detection, mitigation, prediction, and response in a multi-stakeholder environment.

Similarly, there can be multiple security issues that may arise with multi-DSP aggregation service provisioning. In the current setup, it is not explicitly considered how the authentication and authorization process of DSCs will take place while making requests from multiple administrative domains. Management of cryptographic credentials for authentication purposes should be carefully designed due to the ad hoc nature of selecting administrative domains. Therefore, key management will be also challenging and should be dynamically performed as per required by the DSCs. Moreover, impersonate attacks on the aggregator could have severe consequences on the entire system. For instance, a malicious tenant can deliberately impersonate an aggregator and generate unnecessary requests to multiple administrative domains by making requests on available capabilities.

To provide strong isolation between services over a multi-tenant/multi-operator infrastructure, another option is to incorporate cryptographically protected multi-level security enablers. Well-defined security policies together with identity and access management schemes are necessary to provide such a strong isolation. In addition to these, there are also more specific security challenges arising related to IBN management in terms of intent profiling, translation, resolution, activation, and monitoring, which should be addressed while incorporating further refinements to the proposed architecture.

Trust is considered as an assurance that one entity holds that another will perform specific actions according to a specific expectation. Considering trust as the foundation of security, it is also noteworthy to maintain a strong trust relationship within such a multi-stakeholder environment and the management of intents among them. In Section V.D, we elaborate our vision of trust management on intent-based scenarios by introducing the concept of Level of Trust (LoT).

TABLE 1. Evaluation of the intent interfaces.

Intent Functionalities	Standard Interfaces			DSM-IME Functional Block
	TM Forum	3GPP	ETSI ZSM	
Setting the intent	SET Intent	Create Intent	Create	Intent CRUD
	GET Intent	Modify Intent	Update	
	Remove Intent	Query Intent	Read	
		Delete Intent	Delete	
		Activate Intent	Activate	Intent Activation/Deactivation
		Deactivate Intent	Deactivate	
		Suspend	MISSING	
		Deactivate		
Reporting on the intent	Report Intent		Notification/Report	Intent Report Management
Negotiating an intent	Judge Intent Notification		Judge	MISSING
	Preference Intent			
	Probe Intent		Feasibility	
	Best Intent		Best	
Intent Profile Handling	Capability Profile Intent Manager			Intent Handling Capability Exposure

V. INTENT-BASED E2E SERVICES MANAGEMENT & ORCHESTRATION USE CASES

With all the elements presented up until this section such as the architectural aspects from the multi-stakeholder, the functional components of the intent-based DSM and the related enablers, together with the security aspects and enablers to secure intents, this section aims to join all these elements and illustrate how they could be used to properly achieve the correct management and orchestration of intent-based E2E services. To this end, four use cases are presented, focusing on intent-driven fulfilment management, intent-driven service evaluation management, the coordination of intent-driven CLs and, finally, the management of trust in intent-based scenarios.

A. E2E INTENT-DRIVEN SERVICE FULFILLMENT MANAGEMENT

Service fulfillment activities are defined as the actions to be done to coordinate and configure the resources needed for offering a service. The service providers have done it designing a static link between the products that they sell and the services that they can build. Now the customers want personalized services, based on digital capabilities, using resources that could be managed from different administrative domains, creating a very complex environment that needs a high degree of automation and coordination. Intent driven service fulfillment simplifies the service management process because it extracts the expectations from the customer and, considering the set of resources and capabilities that could manage, creates a dynamic design of the service, performs the deployment of resources and initiates a detailed monitoring process for maintaining the service level at a proper level.

The E2E service management process starts when a tenant has some expectations about a product or service and requests it from a DSP, that could manage those expectations,

offering a personalized service based on the capabilities that could manage. The steps and interactions needed to perform the E2E process between the DSP and the tenant are detailed below (see Fig. 5):

- 1) The interaction among DSP and tenants starts with the request of the tenant. This proposal could state a clear definition of the expectations. Alternatively, expectations need to be recovered from a NLP (Natural Language Processing) service plus an intent interpreter system that could extract the expectations and targets involved, an object (network, service) to be deployed with an expected performance associated with a handled capability supported by the DSP.
- 2) When the expectation is clear it could be modeled with the 3GPP intent definition and used with a request ready for the Intent Based Management API that offers the DSP.
- 3) The DSP receives the request and needs to validate and handle the request with the rules defined by the provider, checking if there are conflicts in the definition of the intent and notifying via Intent Report functionality this fact.
- 4) The DSP executes the Intent Matching functionality where performs a context evaluation of the tenant running services and the low-level services definitions and available resources based on the expectation and target in the tenant request, using the Service Portfolio and 3P Profiling elements.
- 5) With full information about the customers’ needs and a clear picture of which could be offered, Intent Translation starts a dynamic design of the fulfillment actions needed, selecting the defined low-level services and establishing the relationships and configuration of the resources involved (some of them could be managed by other administrative entities). Also, e2e KPI and the monitoring activities should be defined

FIGURE 5. Intent Provision Process.

- to achieve a good performance when the service starts with closed loop automation assets.
- 6) The service defined in the previous step could be activated in several ways: at a fixed time, with an event or with another start activity. Before it, an action of Feasibility Check will be evaluated by the DSP. After the evaluation, a report is generated with a detailed explanation about the feasibility process.
 - 7) After positive feasibility, the service is activated and starts to offer its functionality to the tenant. Several metrics and KPIs are collected by the Intent Close Loop elements. The service will run in a dynamic way, changing its behavior in the defined close loop to achieve the performance required in the expectations.
 - 8) The fulfillment process is reported by the Intent Report module that recovers information from the close loop and exposes it to the tenant. The tenant, with that information, could manage the service received and perform actions like deactivation and termination.

B. E2E INTENT-DRIVEN SERVICE EVALUATION MANAGEMENT

Considering the deployment of services based on the defined intent, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the intent fulfillment is required. Such an evaluation has to be continuous and be offered in real-time. To achieve so, the high-level intents have to be translated to specific Service Level Objectives (SLOs) that can be continuously monitored. However, monitoring and assessment of the intent satisfaction is challenging, considering the distributed nature of the deployed networks services and applications and

the activation of multiple orchestration components over the available infrastructure that spans across the computing continuum.

Under this perspective, it can be claimed that is of paramount importance to efficiently translate user needs into actionable objectives and continuously optimize service configurations. With the availability of a representation of user intents, the system can identify relevant metrics that are key for meeting the specified SLOs. In case of failure to fulfill the defined intent or if anomalies are detected in the service's normal operation, the system should conduct a root cause analysis to pinpoint the issues and suggest/take appropriate mitigation actions.

The E2E Intent-driven Service Evaluation Management aims to fill these gaps by combining the identification of intent-related metrics, real-time data fusion of heterogeneous observability signals and orchestration enablers to guarantee the fulfillment evaluation and lifecycle management of services in the computing continuum. These features enable the system to adapt dynamically to changing network conditions and demands. For instance, if the service-level configuration needs adjustment, an orchestration agent can automatically identify the configurations that are needed and implement the necessary changes if possible. Similarly, if infrastructure-level configuration adjustments are required, the corresponding orchestration agents take the appropriate actions to ensure seamless service delivery and performance.

The service operates through a series of enablers that facilitate different aspects of intent-driven orchestration. An observability data fusion mechanism focuses on translating low-level information into fulfillment evaluation values and

FIGURE 6. E2E service evaluation and management enabler interaction.

monitoring service normal operation and continuity. Collaboration among multiple agents is envisaged to support orchestration decisions and actions, considering both local (e.g., within a specific cluster) and global objectives (e.g., for the overall reserved infrastructure across the computing continuum). Indicative actions may regard autoscaling and migration of part of the provided service, ensuring efficient resource utilization and service performance. Intent-driven placement tackles the issue of translating intent into performance efficient placement directives, while intent translation can make the connection between a high-level service description and low-level fulfillment evaluation.

These enablers work in tandem to provide a robust framework for managing complex network environments and ensuring the fulfillment of user intents. The interactions of these enablers can be seen in Fig. 6.

C. E2E INTENT-DRIVEN CLOSED LOOP COORDINATION

1) SINGLE-DSP SCENARIO

Fig. 7 shows the CLs within the Digital Service Management framework where each level implements automation mechanisms to guarantee the automatic fulfillment of service requirements.

At the level of the DSP, the CL are basically business-level loops, aiming at guaranteeing the constraints negotiated in the SLAs. In the Capability Operators, the CL are service-oriented with the main focus on technical constraints such as QoS parameters for services deployed across different Capability Providers. At the lower level, in the Capability Providers, the automation mechanisms mainly consider the status of the resources, e.g., network, computing, etc. With reference to the figure, it can be noted that a single service

request at DSP can generate multiple CLs in all parts of the hierarchy, which allows their coexistence at the same time, in the same domain, and in all the levels: multiple services belonging to different tenants generate dozens of coexisting CLs which may enforce conflictual configurations. CL Governance and Coordination are 2 CL management functions defined to guarantee automatic tuning of the systems while minimizing the risk of system instability [15]. The CL Governance offers specific interfaces to allow third parties (i.e., entities not belonging to the loop such as CL Coordination or orchestrators) to interact with the loop for e.g., configuration, status retrieval, start and stop, etc. The Coordination function incorporates an internal logic dedicated to the management of multiple CL, which includes functionalities to avoid/mitigate conflicts and mechanisms to enable collaboration between loops. The loop is created at orchestration time and, once its provisioning is completed, the CL Governance notifies the CL Coordination function that the CL is up and running, specifying its characteristics, such as configuration, goals, etc. DSP and COP implement their own CL Coordination functions so that each provider coordinates its own internal loops, business and service respectively. Nevertheless, given the relationship between the two entities, as represented in Fig. 7, additional considerations are required.

The IF in the architecture represents the communication system between the actors at the different levels, which allows to create flatness in the hierarchy of the providers. In particular, the DSP and the COP belongs to the same administrative domain (e.g., a network operator covering both roles) and access to the same information related to the Resource Providers, including monitoring data: this implies that both DSP and COP CLs, insisting on the same set of resources, may reacts to the same events generating system instability. This creates a challenging situation where the coordination is no more between CLs rather between CL Coordination functions belonging to different entities, a use case also mentioned by ETSI ZSM [15]. Such a coordination mechanism between coordinators requires i) awareness, i.e., each coordination function must know the other, ii) interaction, i.e., the functions must be able to communicate, and iii) a common set of information related to the CLs.

Fig. 8 illustrates how the CL provisioning and their registration to the CL Coordination changes to address new coordination context.

When a Tenant triggers a provisioning request at DSP, the corresponding intent is orchestrated and triggers the creation of a business-oriented CL at DSP and, in parallel, a Service provisioning request at COP (1)(2). The DSP CL is registered to the CL coordination function (3) while at the COP the service is orchestrated, creating related CLs (one or more) (4)(5). At (6) COP CL Coordination is notified: at this point it notifies its own homologue at DSP, through the IF, about the creation of service’s CLs related to a given

FIGURE 7. Closed Loops within the Digital Service Management framework.

FIGURE 8. CL coordination functions' interaction at orchestration time.

business CL. The workflow for the decommissioning follows similar steps. At runtime, the coordination can be two-fold: i) conflict mitigation/avoidance and ii) collaboration.

In (i) the CL Coordination at DSP is assisted by the Intent Conflict Detection/Resolution modules, belonging to the Intent Fulfilment set of service. When a conflict is detected, the CL Coordination logic decides the mitigation actions, in the case the affected CLs all belong to the DSP. The CL Coordination exploits the interfaces provided by the CL governance to steer the CLs' execution, avoiding race conditions and conflicting decisions. It may happen the case where the conflict is between DSP and COP CLs, as shown in Fig. 9. In this case, both the CLs react to the same input from the IF, trying to enforce some decision on the respective orchestrators (1). To avoid conflicting decisions, simple strategy is to give priority to the CL belongs to the DSP. Once the decision is enforced at the

FIGURE 9. Race condition between CLs at DSP and COP layers.

DSP, the consequent request of service modification at COP (2) results into a modification of its dedicated CL. So, the existing COP CL will be stopped and modified to fit service modification (3)(4), while the Service Orchestration will resolve any potential inconsistencies created by the execution of the previous CL.

With respect to the case (ii), ETSI ZSM considers three types of collaboration: the Delegation, where a hierarchically higher CL (e.g., DSP CL) delegates its goal to a lower layer CLs (e.g., COP) and the Escalation, representing the

FIGURE 10. Inter-layer CL Cooperation through escalation towards DSP CL coordination.

opposite case. The third type of collaboration studied by ETSI ZSM, Peer-to-Peer, involves CLs at the same level of hierarchy. As for the conflict, also in collaboration the base idea is that the higher layer takes the final decision and, as consequence, the form of collaboration considered is the Escalation, from COP to DSP. The collaboration between loops is applied when the coordination module detects that one loop is not able to fulfill its own goal or, in general, another loop may be more effective than another. In this case, the CL Coordination at COP detects that a given loop cannot fulfill its own goal (and no other CLs at the same level can do that). At this point the CL Coordination at COP level notifies the one at the DSP that any adjustment should be performed by the correspondent business-oriented CL. This operation is shown in Fig. 10. A more complex example is represented in Fig. 11: in this case, the, the CL Coordination at COP takes advance of the Escalation to solve a local CL conflict. In the figure are represented several loops grouped by services (green and yellow). At the COP level, CLs belonging to yellow service start conflicting with the one belonging to the green service and the CL governance requests the intervention of the local CL Coordination which, in this example, is not able to solve the conflict. As consequence, the COP CL Coordination escalates to its own homologue at the DSP, which will act to the local CLs in order to enforce corrective action at the DSP resulting into a tuning of the service at COP and the consequent update of the CLs at that level.

FIGURE 11. Inter-layer CL conflict mitigation through escalation.

2) MULTI-DSP SCENARIO

In the Multi-DSP Aggregation scenario, the Tenant-1 Type (Aggregator) is in charge of coordinating a set of required intents in order to deliver a complete service towards the vertical client or final user. Each intent is fulfilled independently by an Intent-based DSM in a SAD. Thus, the operational scope of CL Governance and CL Coordination is limited within one administrative domain, where they share the same information of resource capabilities and monitoring data. On the other hand, the Multi-DSP Federation scenario delegates the responsibility of intent coordination to the Intent-based DSM that receives the request. If the selected Intent-based DSM's local resource is not eligible to fulfil the vertical service on its own, DSMs from other known SADs are invoked to contribute their resource capabilities. In this case, the leading DSM not only manages its CL but also monitors other DSMs' CLs status in order to have an overview of the E2E intent provisioning process. The intent object and CL information must be kept consistent and available among involved parties. Moreover, the order of intent executions can be efficiently organized by the leading DSM and informed to assigned DSMs so that they are aware of their roles in the process. Additionally, any deviation between the operating resources and the declared intent object, CL information, intent delivery pipeline, must trigger an autonomous reconciliation. As a result, the Declarative Intent Reconciliation (DIR) enabler, presented in Section IV.C, is essential for this purpose and its function is shown in Fig. 12.

When the leading DSM receives an intent request from the tenant and determines that external resources are needed, it follows the workflow outlined in Section III.B to identify the required participants. Once all participants have been

FIGURE 12. Closed-Loop Coordination for Multi-DSP.

selected, the DIR module in the leading DSM creates a repository on the Version Control System (VCS) (i.e., Git server) with the intent object description and registers the contributors to deliver the E2E service. All related DSMs are notified by the VCS, then each DSM pushes its Business CL created by the CL Governance to the VCS. In addition, DIR constructs a workflow to specify the optimal execution order to ensure service delivery. Once the leading DSM pushes this pipeline description to the repository, the intent delivery process is activated. VCS oversees invoking corresponding DSMs according to the declared workflow. The final step of the pipeline corresponds to the creation of the intent. If a conflict arises in one or more domains that could necessitate changes in CL goals or actions, the CL Coordinator and CL Governance inform the affected DSMs’ DIR modules with a new version of the Business CL. The DIR then pushes this update to the VCS, where the new desired state is recorded. Also, it is important to note that DSMs use Intent-DSP APIs as the communication channel for managing intents as described in the workflow in Section III. Meanwhile, communication between DSM DIR modules and the VCS is specifically intended for notifications, as well as for intents, CLs, and pipeline information updates.

D. MANAGEMENT OF TRUST ON INTENT-BASED SCENARIOS

Multi-stakeholder scenarios introduce plenty of benefits to be employed by innovative 6G-oriented solutions. Nevertheless, such scenarios also entail avant-garde challenges to properly face, e.g., unreliable relationships due to the number of entities and domains with which we may establish communications with. To overcome unsuitable decision-making, trust is envisioned as a solution to bridge the gap of uncertainty in multi-stakeholder and cross-domain scenarios [18], as the one boost by 6G networks. For this purpose, Hexa-X [19]

FIGURE 13. High-level overview of LoT functionalities.

and Hexa-X-II [20] conceived trustworthiness as a KVI to support the security, privacy, and trust of 6G systems.

In particular, the Level of Trust (LoT) concept is one of the foundations of the Hexa-X-II aim to address the trustworthiness KVI. It intends to assess the security of network services in future 6G networks. To this end, the LoT Assessment Function (LoTAF) plays a key role in enhancing security by analyzing the use of applicable security technologies. It serves as a neutral and bidirectional service, catering to both trustors (users), those whom it aids in making informed decisions, and trustees (network providers), those whom it

offers insights into compliance with trust requirements and opportunities for improving service quality.

LoTAF is oriented towards Computing Continuum to ensure trustworthy end-to-end (E2E) connections across multiple domains and providers and follows well-known standards like ITU-T Y.3057 [21] to manage trust systems ICT infrastructure and services. Furthermore, LoTAF also pursues the Service Assurance for IBN architecture [19] as it is the engine that drives us to obtain quantitative attributes, so it may be associated with the Intent CL Monitoring component of the DSM functionalities. When it comes to the LoT functionalities in terms of trust management, they are divided into two principal blocks (see Fig. 13): i) semi-natural trust-based intent and ii) Level of Trust Assessment Function.

The former is principally centered on semantic understanding, mapping, and representation activities. Thereby, this block is the entry point for end-users through a GUI in which they may write using natural language their trust requirements. To guarantee proper comprehension of requirements, this block makes use of a trust-based interpreter to analyse user requests as well as discover certain essential tokens for finding out what network services fulfil them. Specifically, a high-level descriptive language together with a tailored Named Entity Recognition (NER) model are leveraged for this purpose. To check the outcomes from our NER model, the trust-based interpreter is going to use two different trust intent consistency approaches: a) one-touch through a chatbot to guide user and facilitate the reception of envisioned tokens or b) zero-touch by minimizing the number of interactions with end-users and using reinforce learning techniques to understand all tokens from a single sentence and only verify minor details. At this point, LoTAF examines the network service catalogue for potential candidates that fulfil trust requirements. It is worth mentioning that the trust requirements might be combined with other already existing intents to perform multiple pre-filtering actions. After selecting all available candidates, the trustor will elect a specific one and a Trust Level Agreement (TLA) will be signed between all parties.

To conclude this first block, a knowledge graph is generated by inserting the information from user intent plus the TLA. Since no trust-driven ontology for Computing Continuum was discovered, it was decided to follow the Linked Open Term methodology [22], used in ETSI SAREF [23], to build one to meet the identified needs. Concerning the DSM-IME functionalities reflected in Fig. 4, the knowledge graph may be contemplated as an event generator that may feed the Intent Reporting of DSM-IME as a semantic network to feed reports. Additionally, it will also store all the information concerning symptoms and health status of network services. Therefore, those new data may reflect deviations from the TLA and inform about the evaluation of the trustworthy KPI in services for achieving the intent expectations.

The latter block puts the spotlight on monitoring assurance and forecast deviation of trust requirements signed on the trust level agreement (TLA). To this end, LoTAF assesses both objective trust indicators (quantitative features), coming from the RFC 9417 theoretical framework [22], and subjective trust indicators (non-technical features), gathered from third-party recommenders, personal experience, or reputation. These two dimensions are collected in the first stage of trustworthiness assessment, i.e., the analysis of a set of available network services in a catalogue. Later, once a trust relationship is up and running, only the objective parameters are contemplated to continuously update the initial LoT computed during the first stage. After collecting all trust indicators, LoTAF leverages Bayesian thinking to figure out membership degrees between the LoT and affinity with pre-defined thresholds established in accordance with the terms of the TLA. Note that this process is not a one-time, but it is continuously executed, using time-windows, during the whole lifecycle of a business relationship. Hence, it is well-aligned with the 3rd Party Service stated in the DSM-IME architecture (see Fig. 4) as it may be used to evaluate the third parties in federation scenarios where it is needed to guarantee the integrity of the service.

Overall, LoTAF constitutes a new and agile way to enhance the security and trustworthiness of 6G network services, empowering users and providers with valuable insights and decision-making support.

VI. ANALYTICAL RESULTS: SLA-BASED INTENT CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

In this section, we present analytical results for SLA-based slice intent conflict handling, focusing on both overall system performance and slice intent perspectives through extensive numerical analysis. To this aim, we study a network scenario with constrained network resources in terms of Transport Network (TN) capacity, spectrum, and computation requirements.

The network encompasses a Core Network (CN) along with distributed Radio Access Network (RAN) nodes. The CN consists of common core Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), and TN connects RAN and CN via a BackHaul (BH) network. To simulate realistic traffic demands, we deploy services from different verticals, each with distinct intent requirements. By profiling these service intents, we interpret the information and map them to their corresponding Network Slices (NSs).

Each service is categorized into one of three service types: Hyper Reliable and Low-Latency Communication (HRLLC), Massive Communication (MC), and Immersive Communication (IC). This classification was used to analyze the specific requirements of each service type, facilitating effective conflict resolution and resource allocation within the network. Next, slice intent translation was modelled together with the creation of customized NSs tailored to meet specific intent expectation target (Fig. 14), which allowed to analyze

FIGURE 14. Customized NSs tailored to meet intent expectation targets.

the specific needs of each service type, understanding about slice intent conflict handling, and their impact on the network performance. To ensure the effectiveness of this approach, a thorough feasibility check to verify the validity of SLA objectives in relation to each NS intent was conducted. This process identifies potential intent conflicts using CL monitoring and validation techniques and resolves them by threshold-based conflict mitigation, injecting varied agreed SLA objectives.

An intent may encompass multiple expectations from DSP, each consisting of multiple expectation targets. In this context, an intent may include intent expectation targets (e.g., throughput, E2E tolerable delay, reliability, etc.). Hence, critical targets for each service according to its profile were specified. For instance, latency and reliability were considered as critical intent targets for HRLLC service, latency and connection density for MC service, and finally, throughput and reliability are set as critical intent target for IC service. By translating these intents into specific network resource requirements—including spectrum, TN capacity, and computational resources for VNFs—the slice intent creation process can be effectively streamlined. To this aim, a slice intent template was created based on these pre-calculated network resource requirements, each imposed by particular service intents, and then assign the translated resources for each intent. To simplify these requirements, VNFs computation requirements including CPU computation cost pertaining to VNFs deployment either at AN or CN were considered. Another constraint is TN routing requirements which involves routing link capacity requirement, delivering traffic towards verticals over a path from CN to RAN. Finally, the total delay experienced by different services in the network that depends mainly on the traffic load, the execution time of VNFs.

Despite the efforts to accommodate these diverse requirements, DSPs may encounter challenges in serving all customers, potentially leading to slice intent conflicts. These conflicts should be promptly identified and reported as part of the CL monitoring and validation module. The conflict status may indicate an infeasible solution due to network

TABLE 2. Simulation setup.

General parameters	
Number of CN, ANs	[1, 12]]
Capacity of links in TN	3GB/s
CPU required for VNFs at CN and ANs	[0.06, 0.04] cycles per GB/s
CPU capacity available at CN and ANs	[200, 30] cycles per GB/s
Intent expectation	Throughput, Latency, Reliability, Connection Density
HRLLC slice intent requirements	
Data rate	1.5Gb/s
Latency	10 - 50ms
Critical intent expectation	latency, reliability
MC slice intent requirements	
Data rate	0.6Gb/s
Latency	20 - 100ms
Critical intent expectation	latency, connection density
IC slice intent requirements	
Data rate	2Gb/s
Latency	100 - 250ms
Critical intent expectation	throughput, reliability

resource constraints and may be induced by a distinct slice intent belonging to the same or a different NS. If a conflict arises due to limited network resources possibly exacerbated by overlapping slice intents from the same or different NSs, dynamic adjustments to NS configurations are essential. For example, relaxing SLA objectives for one slice can enable fulfillment of SLAs for a higher-priority NS.

The tests designed aim to handle intent conflicts among different NSs, fulfilling their expectation targets as SLA objectives. They include intent expectation and its corresponding targets in the network as contracted SLA objectives to meet their targets:

- The first intent expectation target requirement is to control the total delay experienced by services in the network to not exceed the maximum tolerable delay of the specific NS.
- The second target is the total throughput of the specific NS that needs to be served and meet the contracted SLA, which imposes minimum throughput for each NS as the intent expectation targets.
- The third intent expectation target is the reliability of each NS, which is translated as achieving a minimum required Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) (in dB).

The intent target considered for slice intents is how much the specific slice has been provisioned successfully. To this end, we study a network scenario composed of a single CN connected through TN (with link capacity of 3 Gb/s) to a set of ANs (12), where we assume AN locations are distributed randomly within the ranges of less than 10 /km to CN. Our analysis focuses on three NSs of HRLLC, MC, and IC, where

the intent requirements along with the simulation setup are summarized in Table 2. Hence, to evaluate the performance of these NSs and identify potential conflicts, critical intent expectation targets of IC NS are applied as SLA objectives in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15 (top) illustrates the impact of imposing throughput and reliability-threshold as intent expectation targets of IC NS to meet SLA objective and for conflicts happening on these intent expectation targets. As seen in this figure (top), enforcing the SLA objectives successfully improved the performance of both throughput and reliability of IC NS. For example, by setting SLA to 30% of throughput and reliability for IC NS, we see an increase of around 2% in the throughput, and an increase of 30% in reliability of IC NS. It is important to note that imposing SLA to more than 50% causes the solution to become infeasible due to insufficient network resources, where available resources may already be consumed by HRLLC and MC NSs.

In parallel, Fig. 15 (bottom) also presents the impact of imposing average throughput and reliability of IC NS as SLA objectives on the performance of accepted services in HRLLC and MC NSs. Indeed, it represents the intent conflicts with the connection density and latency of HRLLC and MC NSs.

This is more evident for SLA threshold ζ 35%, where, for example, the amount of connection density reduction goes up to 65% for HRLLC and MC NSs, while the gain in the throughput goes up to 12% for IC NS. This figure further reveals that although imposing SLA for IC NS leads to conflict with connection density and latency of HRLLC and MC NSs, a relaxation of the SLA objectives for IC NS to 25% or 30% effectively mitigates these intent conflicts. Specifically, there is no longer any conflict with connection density of either HRLLC or MC NSs. As for latency, once SLA objective is set to 25%, there is no conflict with latency of HRLLC and the resulting conflict with MC NS becomes negligible.

Based on the previous results, DSP must be aware of the presented trade-off, and so, DSPs must use the received insights to predefine/reconfigure network resources, prioritizing critical intents while mitigating detected conflicts by relaxing SLA objectives. This ensures an optimal balance between service delivery and resource constraints.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The next generation of networks are clearly pointing towards an improvement in the management and orchestration of the resources in terms of automation and efficiency. To this end, this paper proposes new directions and possibilities towards the design and use of intent-based management and orchestration systems to keep evolving the current networks towards a more autonomous and better performing systems. To do so, this paper presented the architecture components, management models and possible enablers that should be able to accomplish the requirements in 6G multi-

stakeholders' scenarios where intent-based technologies aim to be applied.

Intent-based management and orchestration look towards the removal of the need for the human actor to know all the technicalities related to the control infrastructure and the resources below to properly manage them to deliver the requested E2E services for final users. Intent-based architectures aim to bring a new level of interaction with the tenants, allowing them to define the needed service and the system to evaluate autonomously if it is possible, and if it is not, to offer similar options that may make the tenants to accept the proposed solution.

To reach this new level of autonomy, this paper presented how the intent-based components in different administrative domains may interact among them by presenting the two identified models: aggregation or federation. In there, while the aggregation allows to keep the key decisions (i.e., to which domain to request one intent or another) at the tenant-layer, the federation model allows the contrary (i.e., more automation) by delegating to the control and management system (i.e., DSM) itself to create the necessary intent-based requests with other DSMs in other domains to deliver the final E2E service.

In addition to that, this paper also presents the key functionalities that a DSM must have to achieve a complete intent-based orchestration. Based on these functionalities, a set of enablers focused on the intent-based services management are introduced with their objectives. Moreover, to complement them, a second set of security-related enablers is also described.

With the two sets of enablers and use cases presented, this paper outlines how intent-based management and orchestration systems should be designed and implemented. Moreover, it also introduced a set of scenarios/cases that allowed to present how the different functionalities (and some of the enablers) would contribute to obtain the maximum performance possible from the advantages generated when using intents. The proposed use cases focus on four key aspects of the intent-based systems: a) the provisioning and fulfilment of an intent, b) the evaluation of the intent to validate it continuously delivers what is expected, c) the management of intent-based CLs, and d) the use of trust parameters to manage secure and trustworthy network services. In addition, and related to the provisioning and CL use cases, a set of experimental results related to the management of conflicts among intent-based network slices is presented to illustrate one of the key aspects when dealing with E2E services with multiple actors involved that must consider the different requirements and needs.

Finally, despite the new architectural design, functionalities and services defined in this paper, there are still open challenges and aspects to be addressed in future works. A first example could be the definition and design of specific policies for the intent conflict resolutions as, to the best of our knowledge, there are some ideas but not standardized

FIGURE 15. Intent-based Network Slice conflict handling evaluation results.

policies. Other challenges would be related to security aspects such as the possible attacks during the life-cycle of an intent or during the intent fulfilment task due to the new abstraction layer to generate the intents based on the information from layers below or simply with the generation of conflicts done on purpose.

REFERENCES

[1] S. Kerboeuf, P. Porambage, A. Jain, P. Rugeland, G. Wikström, M. Ericsson, D. Thai Bui, A. Outtagarts, H. Karvonen, P. Alemany, R. Muñoz, R. Vilalta, P. Botsinis, A. Ramos, J. Castaneda Cisneros, M. Karaca, C. Karousatou, S. Barmounakis, P. Demestichas, A. Zafeiropoulos, I. Tzanettis, S. Papavassiliou, P. G. Giardina, G. Landi, B. Han, A. Nimr, and M. A. Uusitalo, "Design methodology for 6g end-to-end system: Hexa-x-ii perspective," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society* **5**, 3368–3394 (2024).

[2] T. Forum, "Intent in autonomous networks. technical report ig 1253. version 1.3.0." Tech. rep., TM Forum (2022).

[3] 3GPP, "Management and orchestration; study on enhanced intent driven management service for mobile networks. v18.0.1," Tech. rep., 3GPP (2023).

[4] C. Janz, N. Davis, D. Hood, M. Lemay, D. Lenrow, L. Fengkai, F. Schneider, J. Strassner, and A. Veitch, "Intent nbi-definition and principles," Tech. rep., Open Networking Foundation (2016).

[5] C. Li, O. Havel, A. O. ad P. Martinez-Julia, J. Nobre, and D. Lopez, "Intent classification," Tech. rep., IETF (2022).

[6] A. Clemm, L. Ciavaglia, L. Granville, and J. Tantsura, "Intent-based networking – concepts and definitions," Tech. rep., IETF (2020).

[7] P. Alemany, R. Muñoz, J.-A. Ordoñez-Lucena, R. Vilalta, D. Lopez, M. Boussard, H. Q. Tran, P. Porambage, R. Pires, H. Blue, J. Malinen, M. Uusitalo, M. Elbamby, M. Abdelaziz, P. Rugeland, J. C. Cisneros, F. Brito, E. D. Biyar, M. Karaca, A. Zafeiropoulos, I. Tzanettis, P. G. Giardina, G. Landi, X. R. Sousa, and S. Kerboeuf, "Multi-stakeholder intent-based service management automation for 6g networks," in *2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, (2024), pp. 866–871.

[8] S. Partners, "From telco to techno: Six tenets for success," Tech. rep., STL Partners (2023).

[9] ETSI, "Etsi gr zsm 011 - zero-touch network and service management (zsm); intent-driven autonomous networks; generic aspects. v1.1.1," Tech. rep., ETSI (2023).

[10] 3GPP, "Management and orchestration; concepts, use cases and requirements. v17.4.0," Tech. rep., 3GPP (2023).

[11] P. Alemany, D. Adanza, L. Gifre, R. Vilalta, and R. Munoz, "Grouping intent-based packet-optical connectivity services," in *49th European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC 2023)*, vol. 2023 (2023), pp. 744–747.

[12] R. Vilalta, D. Adanza, C. Manso, P. Alemany, L. Gifre, R. Casellas, R. Martínez, and R. Muñoz, "Demonstration of intent-based networking for end-to-end packet optical cloud-native sdn orchestration," *IET Conference Proceedings* **2023**, 1738–1741 (2023).

[13] ETSI, "Etsi gr zsm 002 - zero-touch network and service management (zsm); reference architecture. v1.1.1," Tech. rep., ETSI (2019).

[14] 3GPP, "Management and orchestration; intent driven management service for mobile networks. v18.2.1," Tech. rep., 3GPP (2023).

[15] ETSI, "Etsi gr zsm 009-1 - zero-touch network and service management (zsm); closed-loop automation. v1.1.1," Tech. rep., ETSI (2021).

[16] Zhenhua Zou and et al., "Interim overall 6g system design," Tech. rep., Hexa-X-II Project Consortium (2024).

[17] T. Forum, "Tmf921 intent api. v1.1.0," Tech. rep., TM Forum (2022).

[18] J. M. J. Valero, V. Theodorou, M. G. Pérez, and G. M. Pérez, "Sla-driven trust and reputation management framework for 5g distributed service marketplaces," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing* **21**, 1863–1875 (2024).

[19] Bahare Masood Khorsand and et al., "Targets and requirements for 6g – initial e2e architecture," Tech. rep., Hexa-X Project Consortium (2022).

[20] R. Vilalta and et al., "Initial design of 6g smart network management framework," Tech. rep., Hexa-X Project Consortium (2024).

[21] M. Kalla, K. Morneault, S. Rengasami, and G. Sidebottom, "ISDN Q.921-User Adaptation Layer," RFC 3057 (2001).

[22] B. Claise, J. Quilbeuf, D. Lopez, D. Voyer, and T. Arumugam, "Service Assurance for Intent-Based Networking Architecture," RFC 9417 (2023).

[23] R. García-Castro, M. Lefrançois, M. Poveda-Villalón, and L. Daniele, "The etsi saref ontology for smart applications: a long path of development and evolution," *Energy Smart Appliances: Applications, Methodologies, and Challenges* pp. 183–215 (2023).